

Dahun Lee^a, Björn Beck^b, Frank Henning^b, In Yong Lee^c and Young-Bin Park^a

^aDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology, Ulsan, Republic of Korea, ^bFraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology, Pfinztal, Germany
^cDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, Dong-A University, Busan, Republic of Korea

Background

- Increase of demand for CFRPs due to its superior mechanical properties
- Thermoset CFRPs : Higher mechanical properties and thermal resistance
- Large-scale products such as wind turbine blade, airplane, automotive panels.

- Resin transfer molding (RTM) is widely utilized for producing thermoset CFRPs but, vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) provide cost-effective manufacturing.
- Defects, particularly dryspots, commonly occur during infusion stage
- Real-time monitoring is essential to ensure full impregnation → defect-free composites

Problem statements

- 1) Is it applicable to large-scale products?
- 2) What approach ensures reliable prediction of diverse flow-front behavior?

Methodology

Experimental setup

- Real-time measurement on 24 channels (thickness, crosswise and lengthwise)
- Set R_0 as atmospheric state and calculate $\Delta R/R_0$ for normalization
- Atmospheric state: 10 min, vacuum state: 10 min, infusion: 55 min

Generative Adversarial Network (GAN)

- Artificial intelligence tools for generating realistic images (e.g., computer vision, design, image synthesis, etc.)

- Generates realistic fake data to fool the discriminator
- Classifies inputs as real or fake; acts as a binary classifier

Results

Electromechanical Behavior

- Resin impregnation on the electrodes → abrupt increase in electrical resistance
- Governing equation : $P_{Compaction} = P_{Applied} - P_{Resin}$ ($P_{Compaction} \uparrow \rightarrow \Delta R/R_0 \downarrow$)
- $P_{Compaction}$ results in changes in electrical network between electrodes.
- Full impregnation was observed based on the gradual increase in electrical resistance.

Flow-front Identification

- Abrupt increase in electrical resistance → identify resin arrival time on electrodes
- Linear equations for identifying resin location along electrodes
 $y_{2left} = v_{2left}(t-5) + y_{1left}$
 $y_{2right} = v_{2right}(t-5) + y_{1right}$
 $y_{1left} = v_{1left}(t-1) + 10$
 $y_{1right} = v_{1right}(t-1) + 10$
- derive parabolic equation and plot to represent flow-front

- Identified result closely matched the actual resin flow behavior.
- Resin flow predicted by numerical analysis was inconsistent with experimental result.

Flow-front Prediction

- 17 possible flow-front scenarios defined across 3 sections.
- While training set was plotted based on linear equations, a GAN produce various configurations.
- Realistic flow-front images were generated using GAN, including racetracking effects.

- Possible resin flow-front scenarios were presented on tree model based on sections.

- The flow-front scenario was determined based on resin arrival time at Section 1.
- Possible resin flow scenarios on Section 2 were identified based on probability.
- Sequential prediction was performed using resin arrival time at electrodes.
- Once the scenario was determined, a GAN generated multiple flow-front configurations to represent the current and its future resin flow behavior.
- Identified flow-front configurations allowed early prediction of potential dry spots.

Conclusions

1. A CFRP panel was monitored during the VARTM process using electromechanical behavior during resin infusion.
2. A novel flow-front identification and prediction method was developed by combining a tree-based decision model with a GAN, enabling accurate sequential identification of resin flow.
3. The model can predict dry spot locations, providing a robust system for real-time defect prevention and improved composite quality.

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